

Additional material for the paper ‘They saw it, onu, 它, coming: An information theoretic study of cross-linguistic variation in personal pronouns’- Appendix C: UD implementation of the pronominal systems

The appendix presents the implementation of the personal pronominal system and its features using the Universal Dependencies framework. Unless otherwise indicated, all lists of forms are extracted from grammars.

Albanian

Manually-compiled list of forms (all forms, clitics). Universal Features for the pronoun type (Prs), gender, person and number. Universal parts of speech (PRON, ADP). Universal Relations.

Arabic

Manually-compiled list of forms (independent forms: Zena Al Khalili, p.c.). Universal Features for the pronoun type (Prs), gender, person and number. Universal parts of speech (PRON). Universal Relations. Extracted pronoun types¹ are checked against a manually-compiled list of forms and translations.

Armenian

Manually-compiled list of forms (all forms). Universal Features for the pronoun type (Prs), gender, person and number. Universal parts of speech (PRON). Universal Relations.

Basque

Manually-compiled list of forms (all forms, uninflected, emphatic vs. non-emphatic forms, number, person). Universal Features for the third person (number). Lemma for inflected forms. Universal parts of speech (PRON, DET). Universal Relations.

Dutch

Manually-compiled list of forms (all forms, unstressed forms, number). UD Features for the pronoun type (Prs) and person. Universal parts of speech (PRON). Language-specific parts of speech for gender, number. Universal Relations.

¹ Type as in ‘token vs. type’.

Greek

Manually-compiled list of forms (all forms, clitics). Universal Features for the pronoun type (Prs), gender, person and number. Universal parts of speech (PRON). Universal Relations.

Hindi

Manually-compiled list of forms (all forms: Aarushi Singhal, p.c.). Universal Features for the pronoun type (Prs), gender, person and number. Universal parts of speech (PRON, DET, ADP). Universal Relations.

Hungarian

Manually-compiled list of forms (incomplete list due to inflectional adposition). Universal Features for the pronoun type (Prs), person and number. Universal parts of speech (PRON). Universal Relations. Extracted pronoun types are checked against a manually-compiled list of forms and translations.

Indonesian

Manually-compiled list of forms (clitics, incomplete list due to inflectional adposition). Universal Features for the pronoun type (Prs), person, number and clusivity. Universal parts of speech (PRON). Universal Relations. Extracted pronoun types are checked against a manually-compiled list of forms and translations.

Irish

Manually-compiled list of forms (stressed forms, incomplete list due to inflectional adpositions). Universal Features for the pronoun type (Person), person, number and gender. Universal parts of speech (PRON, ADP). Language-specific parts of speech (inflectional adpositions). Universal Relations. Extracted pronoun types are checked against a manually-compiled list of forms and translations.

Italian

Manually-compiled list of forms (all forms). Universal Features for the pronoun type (Prs), gender, person, number and clitics. Universal parts of speech (PRON). Universal Relations.

Japanese

Manually-compiled list of forms (all forms, person, number, gender, Dyer: p.c.). Universal parts of speech (PRON). Universal Relations. Extracted pronoun tokens are automatically filtered for possessive (nmod in Universal Relations) forms.

Lithuanian

Manually-compiled list of forms (all forms). Universal Features for the pronoun type (Prs), gender, person and number. Universal parts of speech (PRON). Universal Relations.

Mandarin

Manually-compiled list of forms (all forms, inclusive vs. exclusive). Universal Features for person and number. Universal parts of speech (PRON). Universal Relations.

Persian

Manually-compiled list of forms (incomplete list). Universal Features for the pronoun type (Person), person and number. Universal parts of speech (PRON). Language-specific parts of speech (clitics vs. independent forms). Universal Relations. Extracted pronoun types are checked against a manually-compiled list of forms (Zohreh Piroozeh, p.c.) and translations.

Turkish

Manually-compiled list of forms (all forms). Universal Features for the pronoun type (Prs), person and number. Universal parts of speech (PRON). Universal Relations.

Ukrainian

Manually-compiled list of forms (all forms). Universal Features for the pronoun type (Prs), gender, person and number. Universal parts of speech (PRON). Universal Relations.